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APPLIED RESEARCH

Leveraging a Vision Transformer and Adversarial Unsupervised Domain Adaptation to Generate the NIR Band on Out-of-Domain VHR RGB

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ABSTRACT The accessibility of very-high-resolution Remote Sensing (RS) near-infrared (NIR) imagery before the 2010s is limited. In addition, public annotated image datasets often used as benchmarks contain only RGB information. Thus, RGB-to-NIR translation could greatly benefit the RS field. Generative adversarial networks (GANs) and, more recently, vision transformers (ViTs) have shown promising results in generating spectrally super-resolved data. However, the RGB-to-hyperspectral studies scatter their attention to multiple bands, whereas the RGB-to-NIR studies have tackled only vegetation. In addition, prior research regarding NIR prediction on out-of-domain data is extremely limited, and attention models have not been previously tested in the RGB-to-NIR translation. Beyond that, unsupervised domain adaptation (UDA) has been overlooked in the enhancement of cross-domain band generation. This study, at first, evaluates a conditional GAN and two attention networks on predicting NIR on out-of-domain RGB data. The properties of the out-of-domain data are those typically required in RS NIR prediction tasks (different regions/sensors/dates). In a following step, the study attempts to increase the source/target RGB radiometric similarity through CycleGAN-based UDA on unpaired bi-temporal data (lack of geographic correspondence in RGB source/target patches), and thus improve the initial NIR prediction. In the experiments, the vegetation, impervious, and ground classes were assessed. It was shown that MST++ (ViT) produced the most satisfactory out-of-domain NIR predictions and that UDA through a CycleGAN version employing batch normalization managed to significantly enhance the NIR prediction when there was a substantial RGB radiometric domain gap.

INDEX TERMS Adaptation model, adversarial machine learning, image generation, infrared imaging, image resolution, multispectral imaging, optical imaging, prediction methods.

I. INTRODUCTION

Image-to-image translation (ITIT) is an image processing method whose basic idea is to learn the mapping functions between an input and an output image [1]. ITIT can be either performed for paired data (pixel co-responsence between input and output image) or unpaired data. Multiple Remote Sensing (RS) studies have investigated paired ITIT through deep learning (DL) and most often conditional generative adversarial networks (cGANs) to generate missing information. The applications are various and among others

include Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) \leftrightarrow optical [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], visible (VIS) \rightarrow map [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], optical \rightarrow elevation (digital terrain/surface model (DTM/DSM)) [15], [16], [17], [18], thermal infrared (TIR) \leftrightarrow VIS [19], [20], [21], [22], VIS-VIS [23], [24], grayscale \rightarrow RGB [25], [26], spectral super-resolution (SSR) (RGB/multispectral (MS) \rightarrow hyperspectral (HS)) [27], [28], [29], [30], [31], [32], [33], [34], [35], [36], [37], [38], and RGB \rightarrow near-infrared (NIR) [39], [40], [41], [42], [43]. Concerning unpaired ITIT, so far, it has been used in Remote Sensing (RS) applications exclusively for unsupervised domain adaptation (UDA) purposes as an intermediate step to enhance the semantic segmentation output [44], [45],

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[46], [47], [48], [49], [50], [51], [52]. It is noted that the arrow symbol (“ \rightarrow ”) in the text refers to the direction of ITIT.

In the following Introduction Subsections, we present the related literature works (I.A-I.C), and then we describe our motivations and contributions (I-D).

A. PAIRED ITIT- BROADLY RELATED WORK

The vast majority of the RS ITIT research has been focused on SAR \leftrightarrow optical paired deep ITIT because SAR data are unaffected by atmospheric conditions. Due to higher accessibility, most of the studies process medium-resolution (≥ 5 m) data [2], [3], [4], [5]. However, recently, a few studies have been conducted on very high-resolution (VHR) data [1], [6], [7], [8], [9]. In [1], aiming at enhancing change detection performance, NICE-GAN [53], an introspective network based on CycleGAN [54] with multi-scale formulation in the discriminator and residual attention, was used for SAR \leftrightarrow optical translation. With the same goal but in a non-adversarial setting, the authors in [6] implemented an optical-SAR domain adaptation-based change detection network where distribution discrepancies in Hilbert space were included. An ITIT adaptation-based change detection technique (based on NICE-GAN) was also proposed in [7], where the features of optical images were transferred to SAR. In [8], the authors took advantage of both Pix2Pix (cGAN) [55] and CycleGAN, and performed SAR \leftrightarrow optical mapping by incorporating an additional network called the distortion-adaptive module in both directions. Finally, in [9], a Parallel-GAN was proposed for SAR \rightarrow optical translation consisting of a backbone ITIT subnetwork and an adjoint optical image reconstruction subnetwork.

Interest has also been shown in the deep translation of VHR VIS satellite images to maps because it could prove very beneficial when timely updates are required [10], [11], [12], [13], [14]. Several methods have been applied in a paired setting. In [10], a scale-consistent cGAN was proposed to simultaneously generate multi-level tile maps from multi-scale RS images. In addition, in [12], adversarial deep transfer training schemes were combined with attention-based network designs to generate maps over various regions, and in [13], a level-aware fusion network for multilevel map generation was introduced. Due to the scarcity of paired data, unpaired samples have also been proven to be useful. In [11], the authors designed a semi-supervised learning strategy based on training GANs on rich unpaired samples and then applied fine-tuning on limited paired samples. In addition, in [14], Semi-MapGen was proposed, a network based on semi-supervised GANs, which requires only a small set of accurate and complete matched data and plenty of unpaired data.

Mapping optical data to elevation information in a paired fashion is another application that has been studied in the DL literature as an affordable alternative to approaches that require Light detection and ranging (Lidar), Interferometric SAR (InSAR), or stereo pairs [15], [16], [17], [18]. The study

described in [15] was among the first to apply a cGAN to translate VHR optical data to elevation. Adversarial learning was also proposed in [16], where Pix2Pix was implemented to map optical to elevation data for Sentinel-2 and autonomous aerial vehicle (AAV) imagery. In a non-adversarial setting, the authors of [17] applied an encoder-decoder model with skip connections [56] and residual blocks [57] for DSM generation. Several strategies were investigated and showed that the performance can vary according to the dataset morphology. Similarly, in [18], a U-Net [56] with residual blocks was applied to create elevation information for airborne images.

Other DL studies of paired data have investigated the TIR \rightarrow VIS ITIT in data collected by geostationary meteorological satellites by use of the Pix2Pix model to enrich the collected information [19], [20], [21]. In [19], Pix2Pix was trained on daytime pairs of the $10.8 \mu\text{m}$ longwave radiance band and the $0.675 \mu\text{m}$ visible band of the meteorological imager (MI) onboard the Communication, Ocean and Meteorological Satellite (COMS), to create the nonexistent nighttime visible reflectance band. In a later study for the above-mentioned satellite [20], Pix2Pix was applied for virtual nighttime visible imagery generation using multiband infrared observations and a brightness temperature difference. In a similar concept, in [21], Pix2Pix was trained on thermal band differences of the Advanced Meteorological Imager (AMI) sensor, of the GK-2A Geostationary Korea Multi-Purpose Satellite, to provide virtual RGB bands during day and night. Besides the above-mentioned low-resolution meteorological applications, VIS \rightarrow TIR VHR mapping by Pix2Pix has also been explored [22] as an intermediate step to achieve thermal geolocation in low illumination environments, motivated by the limited availability of satellite thermal data.

Data collected by geostationary meteorological satellites have also been used for cross-satellite deep paired VIS-VIS ITIT with the Pix2Pix network to generate missing bands [23], [24]. In [23], Pix2Pix was trained on blue band radiance images of the Advanced Himawari Imager (AHI) to generate a simulated green band (useful for monitoring water and vegetation) for the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES-16) Advanced Baseline Imager (ABI) sensor. In addition, in [24], Pix2Pix was trained on blue band radiance images of the GK-2A/AMI sensor to generate simulated green and red bands (useful for monitoring atmospheric environments) for the Geostationary Environment Monitoring Spectrometer (GEMS) of the GK-2B satellite.

B. PAIRED ITIT- CLOSELY RELATED WORK

1) SSR

Hyperspectral images carry valuable spectral information. However, the fact that until very recently satellites that provide global and public HS data were nonexistent and the high cost of airborne sensors hinders the exploitation of HS information. Thus, hyperspectral image reconstruction from low-cost RGB cameras and MS sensors (spectral super-resolution (SSR)) has attracted recent attention. In the

past, the problem was approached in a non-DL manner with linear unmixing [58], regression [59], and methods that exploit sparse representations and dictionary learning [60], [61]. More recently, numerous DL studies have been published [27], [28], [29], [30], [31], [32], [33], [34], [35] [36], [37], [38]. All SSR literature methods so far have evaluated their paired methodologies in the output as a whole without isolating particular bands (e.g., NIR).

In [27], a variant of the dense convolutional neural network (CNN) called “Tiramisu” [62] was trained on MS data collected from the Advanced Land Imager (ALI) on board the Earth Observing One (EO-1) satellite to predict the HS Hyperion bands. The qualitative evaluation showed that the predicted output was less noisy than the ground-truth data. In addition, the quantitative evaluation employed abundance estimation. In [28], CNN regression models were investigated to produce the Hyperion HS bands from the Landsat 7/8 MS bands. The authors showed that the CNN regression produced better performance compared to conventional regression methods. The model outputs were also evaluated by classification with support vector machines (SVM) over principal components (PCs). In [29], the authors proposed a cGAN with an additional spectral discriminator to map RGB to HS information in GF-5 data. The quantitative spectral and spatial scores showed that the proposed network was more robust than alternative non-adversarial approaches. In [30], an encoder-decoder model with attention to semantic similarity was implemented to spectrally super-resolve RGB to HS images in 1 m spatial resolution (SR). MS→HS SSR (Hyperion images) by employing semantic information was also proposed in [31] in the form of a change detection subnetwork. Finally, an encoder-decoder model was trained in [32] to spectrally super-resolve AAV and GF-5 MS images. Several input band combinations were explored, and it was shown that the inclusion of the NIR band can enhance the performance of the final HS output.

In other studies [33], [34], [35], SSR attempts have been made to enhance the exploitation of both spatial and spectral information in high/medium SR data. In [33], the authors proposed a progressive spatial-spectral joint network to reconstruct satellite and airborne HS data from MS. In addition, in [34], a spatial-spectral residual attention was exploited for MS→HS mapping, and in [35], a spatial-spectral feature attention module was introduced in a GAN for both synthetic and real data scenarios.

More recently, attention modules have also been exploited [36], [37], [38]. In [36], a hybrid transformer architecture was explored to achieve SSR on two aerial datasets through the integration of intra- and cross inter- row/column attention mechanisms. In [37], a reflectance/shading decomposition SSR framework that incorporated spatial and channel attention modules was tested on AVIRIS and GF5 data. Finally, in [38], the authors employed an integrated network of 3D CNN and U-shaped Transformer in a coarse-to-fine scheme to utilize both local and global information in aerial imagery.

2) RGB-TO-NIR TRANSLATION

The RS studies published so far in RGB→NIR paired translation have focused exclusively on vegetation applications [39], [40], [41], [42], [43], [63]. The significance of the NIR band in providing rich information for the determination of vegetation parameters has long since been established [64], [65], [66], [67]. In the last years, MS sensors onboard AAVs have been extensively used in precision agriculture. However, small producers have difficulty in affording the required equipment. Low-cost RGB cameras on board lightweight AAVs are a more affordable option [41]. Thus, RGB→NIR translation could prove very useful for vegetation monitoring.

Before the broad application of DL, this problem had been approached by regression analysis on conventional cameras depicting crops [63], where a green-NIR correlation had been indicated. In recent years, several DL studies have been published for the RGB→NIR translation in vegetation areas, and the vast majority have employed the Pix2Pix model [39], [40], [41], [42], [43]. In [39], Pix2Pix was trained on AAV RGB crop data to generate the NIR band. The L1 loss was replaced with the Charbonnier penalty function, and both in- (same crop type) and out-of-domain (different crop types) experiments were performed. In [40], RGB→NIR translation was performed on Worldview-2 data by Pix2Pix with residual blocks in the generator. The authors focused on forest areas and evaluated the performance in a cross-domain setting (SPOT, Planet with finetuning). The Planet data translation showed lower evaluation scores due to higher heterogeneity compared to the training inputs. It was also stated that adversarial training increased the performance and that the inclusion of NIR in the classification task lowered the size of the needed annotations. One of the research motivations was the fact that public RGB databases do not contain the NIR band. However, ITIT could generate the missing information. In [41], Pix2Pix was trained on low-cost AAV RGB cameras to estimate the NIR band for agricultural purposes. The network outperformed a previously proposed endmember-based method [68]. The authors also investigated combinations of the original L1 loss with the structural similarity index (SSIM) and a perceptual loss to achieve slightly better results. In [42], Pix2Pix was employed for RGB→NIR field imagery translation (agricultural areas) with a DenseNet architecture [62] as the generator. Comparison with the original U-Net generator showed slight improvement. Finally, in [43], RGB→NIR translation was performed on Sentinel-2 data collected all year round. It was observed that the model was unaffected by corrupted pixels but did not show satisfactory generalization ability to Landsat-8 data. The failure in the out-of-domain performance could be attributed to differences in illumination, as well as atmospheric and sensor conditions.

C. UDA

Unpaired ITIT has recently been widely used in the form of UDA in VHR VIS RS when annotations are available in the source domain but not in the target domain [44],

[45], [46], [47], [48], [49], [50], [51], [52]. The goal is to enhance cross-domain object detection (CDOD) or semantic segmentation (CDSS) tasks by decreasing domain shifts caused by the rich structure diversity, the variability in atmospheric/lighting conditions and viewing angles, as well as the different sensor characteristics.

Adversarial approaches and particularly CycleGAN-based models, which employ a cycle-consistency loss, have often been proposed [44], [45], [46], [47], [48]. In [44], the segmentation models were optimized in two opposite directions by implementing bidirectional adversarial domain adaptation through CycleGAN, which takes advantage of the information from both domains. In [45], a CycleGAN-based model with residual connections was proposed, followed by a semantic segmentation stage. An in-network resizer module was included to address the scale discrepancy. In [46], a two-stage cross-domain self-training object detection framework was investigated. The first stage introduced a CycleGAN-based strategy to mitigate the domain-shift and increase the quality of pseudo-labels. In [47], the two-stage CDSS task was approached by a dual space CycleGAN-based model where frequency information through discrete wavelet transform was integrated. Finally, in [48], CycleGAN-based UDA was explored to overcome the limitations of a coastal marine debris estimation model.

In other studies, adversarial learning has been applied, without the cyclic-consistency loss, or alternative non-adversarial learning strategies have been employed [49], [50], [51], [52]. In [49], CDSS was performed by a curriculum-style local-to-global cross-domain adaptation framework. The adaptation process was conducted in an easy-to-hard way using an entropy-based score and adversarial learning. In [50], a two-stage framework was applied, which performs fine-grained local and category-level alignment on top of global alignment. The framework used adversarial learning and knowledge distillation. In [51], the authors proposed a deep covariance alignment model to align category features. Finally, in [52], the authors implemented a lightweight UDA model relying on latent representation separation and mixing across domains, which can be used in a one-shot setting.

D. MOTIVATIONS AND CONTRIBUTIONS

Before the 2010s, the accessibility of VHR RS NIR imagery was limited since most of the airborne data collected until that time contained only RGB information, and satellite VHR data were not yet available to the public. In addition, public image datasets like Google Earth and several annotated datasets (e.g. [69], [70], [71]), which are often used as benchmarks, contain only RGB information. Thus, artificially generating the missing NIR band could greatly benefit RS applications when: a) requiring the use of RGB airborne data collected before 2010s (e.g. change detection) or publicly available in Google Earth; and b) exploring the performance of novel methods on public annotated RGB benchmark datasets after enriching them with the NIR band.

As mentioned in the above literature review, the SSR-published studies have evaluated their paired data methodologies in the output as a whole without isolating particular bands like the NIR. In addition, to the best of our knowledge, the RGB→NIR literature in total has exclusively explored only the vegetation category. However, the NIR information has also among others proven useful for general scene recognition [72], mineral mapping [73], plastic litter detection [74], [75], and nighttime image generation for the monitoring of environmental and socio-economic dynamics [76]. Thus, the generation of the NIR band would be significant to be explored in more detail and for more land cover categories. In addition, the evaluation of the methods on out-of-domain data is crucial since in typical RS applications the NIR prediction is required on data collected on dates different than those of the training set or referring to different regions with similar spectral characteristics. In both cases, atmospheric optical depth and sun/sensor viewing angle may differ, resulting in radiometric differences (radiometric domain gap).

Concerning UDA, since it has been irrefutably recognized as capable of decreasing the domain discrepancies in the CDSS task, it should be at least logical to test it for the enhancement of cross-domain band generation (e.g., NIR). The objective is to increase the radiometric similarity between the training set (source data) and the out-of-domain set (target data) through UDA, thereby improving the NIR prediction of the out-of-domain set. A practical common scenario would be training a model with recent satellite RGB (input), NIR (output) data, and then applying UDA on airborne RGB past data as a pre-step before using the pretrained model to generate the unavailable past NIR. Unlike the CDSS/CDOD tasks, where spectral similarity is not required when applying UDA (e.g. applying an SS model trained on green roofs (labeled source data) to detect red→green roofs (UDA) (unlabeled target data)), in the cross-domain band generation spectral similarity between the source and target data when applying UDA is significant to predict a reliable missing band.

Attempting to contribute to the previous VHR RGB→NIR prediction literature, this paper evaluates at first, a conditional GAN (cGAN) and two attention networks trained on paired data (pixel correspondence between RGB and NIR) on predicting NIR on out-of-domain RGB data, and then attempts to improve the NIR prediction by employing a CycleGAN-based UDA on unpaired RGB bi-temporal data. The unpaired process follows a more general scenario where the source and target RGB patches used in the CycleGAN training do not geographically correspond. In summary, the main contributions can be summarized as follows:

- 1) We investigate the performance of a cGAN and two attention models on predicting NIR on out-of-domain VHR RGB data referring to different regions/sensors/dates than the training set. Prior research regarding NIR prediction on out-of-domain data is extremely limited. In addition, attention models have not been previously tested in the RGB→NIR translation.

2) We explore the possibility of UDA through CycleGAN in improving the NIR prediction on out-of-domain imagery. In three configurations, the effects of batch size and normalization techniques are examined. Through this study, UDA is employed for the first time in the enhancement of cross-domain band generation.

3) We implement the models on three main thematic categories: a) impervious surfaces/urban fabric (manmade objects); b) vegetation (forest, crops); and c) ground. In earlier work, the impervious and ground categories have been completely out of focus.

In the following sections, at first the data and methodology are described (section II), and then the results are presented and discussed (section III). Finally, the conclusions are summarized (section IV).

II. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

A. DATASETS – PRE-PROCESSING

For the implementation of the methodology, Geoeye-1 (GE01) and Worldview-2/3 (WV-2/3) satellite VHR images were employed. The procured images were pan-sharpened by the vendor and contained four bands (RGB-NIR). The spatial resolution for GE01 and WV-2 images was 0.5 m, whereas for WV-3 it was 0.3 m. They were collected from four European areas (Granada/Spain (G), Tønsberg/Norway (T), Rhodes/Greece (R), Venice/Italy (V)) in a bi-temporal fashion. The areas were heterogeneous since the morphology differed (G: dense high urban fabric/red-tiled roofs/steep mountains/few agricultural fields, T: sparse low buildings/grey-tiled roofs/flat terrain/high presence of agriculture and forest, R: dense urban fabric with terraces/few crops, V: very dense homogeneous buildings/red-tiled roofs/limited vegetation). More info can be found in [77], where this dataset was used for the first time. In the text, “1” refers to the earliest date and “2” to the latest (e.g., G1, T2).

The pre-processing steps included: a) the creation of mosaics for WV-3 since the area of interest was depicted in multiple tiles; b) resampling of the WV-3 images to 0.5 m SR (same as GE01, WV2); c) conversion of image values to 8-bit radiometric resolution (often encountered on airborne images before 2010s and public datasets); and

TABLE 1. Dataset information.

Area	Collection date	Satellite	Spatial Resolution (m)	Size (km ²)
Granada	19/7/2013	GE01	0.5	21
	2/7/2018	WV-3	0.3	
	20/9/2013	WV-2	0.5	
Tønsberg	12/7/2019	GE01	0.5	25
	23/4/2013	WV-2	0.5	
Rhodes	5/6/2019	WV-3	0.3	33
	4/5/2013	GE01	0.5	
Venice	13/5/2018	WV-2	0.5	17

d) normalization. Table 1 shows details about the images. Water areas were masked and not taken into account because they were out of the focus of this study.

B. METHOD

In this paper, after evaluating a cGAN (Pix2Pix), an adaptive weighted attention network (AWAN) [78], and a ViT (MST++) [79] trained on paired data (each pixel in the RGB source data corresponds to a pixel in the target NIR data) on predicting NIR on out-of-domain data, a CycleGAN-based UDA was employed on unpaired data to improve the NIR prediction on out-of-domain imagery. Pix2Pix and CycleGAN were selected because they have been widely used in the ITIT literature, and AWAN and MST++ because they won the NTIRE Spectral Reconstruction Challenge in 2020 and 2022, respectively. The models were implemented in Pytorch [80], on a machine with an i7-8700K CPU and an NVIDIA 1070 Ti GPU. A flowchart of the methodology is provided in Fig. 1.

In more detail, after the data pre-processing, the paired ITIT was applied (Fig. 1/ Paired ITIT (1)), where Pix2Pix, AWAN, and MST++ were trained on RGB data to predict NIR. All models were trained on the G1 image alone. The performance of the G1-trained models was assessed on seven out-of-domain images (G2, R1, R2, T1, T2, V1, V2). This evaluation permits giving a performance estimation in scenarios where the unavailable NIR image corresponds to a region spectrally similar to a region with available NIR. A possible application could be in the NIR enrichment of annotated benchmark public RGB datasets.

Following the paired ITIT, the unpaired ITIT was applied (UDA) by training three CycleGAN versions (IN1, IN14, BN14) on the RGB images of Granada and Venice. The effect of different normalization techniques (batch normalization (BN), instance normalization (IN)) and batch sizes (1, 14) was evaluated. The process is unpaired because the G1 RGB patches during the model training did not correspond geographically to the G2 RGB patches (random selection). The same goes for V1/V2. This approach covers a more challenging general scenario.

The above pairs were selected because they were collected in the same month to avoid seasonal changes. The UDA aimed at adapting G2 data to G1, and V2 data to V1, and thus increasing RGB radiometric similarity based: a) on the logical assumption that the G1-trained models (Fig. 1/ Paired ITIT (1)) should perform better on G1 compared to G2, since G1 was the training set; and b) based on the fact that the G1-trained models performed better on V1 compared to V2 (section III). G2 and V2 are considered out-of-domain data compared to G1 because G2 is collected by a different sensor and on a different date, and V2 refers to a different region. Since CycleGAN uses a cyclic loss function, the reverse adaptation is also implemented during training, but it is not of interest in this paper.

The ultimate objective of UDA was to enhance the NIR prediction of G2 and V2 in the paired ITIT. Thus, after UDA,

FIGURE 1. Flowchart of the methodology.

a second inference was performed on the G1-trained Pix2Pix, AWAN, and MST++ models (Fig. 1. /Paired ITIT (2)) where the NIR G2 and V2 predictions were compared with the initial predictions (before UDA). It is noted that besides the CycleGAN-based UDA, histogram matching (HM) was also performed for comparison.

1) PAIRED ITIT – PIX2PIX

GANs are generative models that learn a mapping from z to output image y , $G : z \rightarrow y$ [81]. GANs consist of a generator G and a discriminator D . In image generation applications, the goal of the generator is to produce synthetic (fake) images that challenge the ability of the discriminator to differentiate them from real images. The training is described by the

objective function shown in (1), where G aims at minimizing L_{GAN} against an adversarial D that aims at maximizing it.

$$\min_G \max_D L_{GAN}(G, D) \quad (1)$$

$$L_{GAN}(G, D) = \mathbb{E}_y [\log D(y)] + \mathbb{E}_z [\log(1 - D(G(z)))] \quad (2)$$

Conditional GANs learn a mapping from the observed image x and random noise vector z , to y , $G : \{x, z\} \rightarrow y$ [55]. In this case, the minmax two-player training is performed with (3).

$$L_{cGAN}(G, D) = \mathbb{E}_{x,y} [\log D(x, y)] + \mathbb{E}_{x,z} [\log(1 - D(x, G(x, z)))] \quad (3)$$

In our study, Pix2Pix, which is a cGAN, was implemented according to the suggestions in [55] with a modification in the

number of convolutional layers. It was trained in an alternating way according to (4), which includes the addition of the L1 loss (5) to (3) so that the generator, except for antagonizing the discriminator, is also tasked to produce outputs similar to the ground-truth (reconstruction loss). In (5), L1 is a trade-off parameter between $L_{cGAN}(G, D)$ and $L_{L1}(G)$ was set to 100.

$$\min_G \max_D L_{cGAN}(G, D) + \lambda L_{L1}(G) \quad (4)$$

$$L_{L1}(G) = \mathbb{E}_{x,y,z} [\|y - G(x, z)\|_1] \quad (5)$$

The generator followed a U-Net [56] architecture. It consisted of eight convolutional layers in the encoder part and eight transposed convolutional layers in the decoder part. The respective layers in the original Pix2Pix implementation were four. In our study, the number was increased in an attempt to improve the prediction accuracy. Skip connections through concatenation were applied between the encoder and the decoder layers. Dropout was used in three decoder layers with a value of 0.5 (randomly zeroes some of the input tensor) to provide stochasticity both in training and inference.

Concerning the discriminator, it consisted of five convolutional layers and was in a PatchGAN form [55]. BN followed the convolutional layers in both the generator and the discriminator. Finally, the dimensions of the generator input patch

TABLE 2. Paired ITIT - training details.

Training details	Pix2Pix	AWAN	MST++
Epochs	50	50	50
Batch size	32	32	10
Patch size	256	64	128
Training steps	1312	350	300
Trainable params G	3,404,801	4,354,045	1,619,625
Trainable params D	175,793	-	-
Training time (h) (G1/all)	3	3	3
GPU memory usage (GB)	1.6	8	7

FIGURE 2. Architecture of the implemented CycleGAN model. In the first version, nine residual blocks were used in the generator, whereas in the second and third, three. The yellow highlighted layers in the discriminator were removed in the second and third versions.

FIGURE 3. Boxplots of the evaluation scores in paired ITIT (first stage). (a) Impervious, (b) Vegetation.

FIGURE 4. Boxplots of the evaluation scores in paired ITIT (first stage) for the ground category.

were $256 \times 256 \times 3$ (RGB) and of the output patch were $256 \times 256 \times 1$ (NIR prediction).

The training details are shown in Table 2. The learning rate was set to 2×10^{-4} . The number of epochs was set to 50 for the G1-trained models. The inference time for a 17 km^2 image was 11 s. The selection of the final weights was performed by an empirical process based on the lowest L1 loss values in combination with the observation of the performance of the predictions on image samples.

2) PAIRED ITIT – AWAN

AWAN contains a backbone with multiple dual residual attention blocks (DRAB). Long and short skip connections form the dual residual learning. An adaptive weighted channel attention (AWCA) module and a patch-level second-order non-local (PSNL) module were investigated to capture channel correlations and long-range spatial context.

In our study, the network was implemented according to the suggestions in [78]. The selected DRAB number was 8, and the selected output channel number for the DRAB was 100. The dimensions of the input RGB patch of the network

were $64 \times 64 \times 3$, and of the output patch were $64 \times 64 \times 1$. It is noted that the original output bands for AWAN were 31, but in our case, it is only the NIR band. To retain consistency with Pix2Pix, L1 loss was used. For fair comparison, it was decided to train for a similar amount of time as Pix2Pix, thus, the number of training steps was set accordingly. The training details are shown in Table 2. The learning rate was set to 1×10^{-4} . The inference time for a 17 km^2 image was 144 s.

3) PAIRED ITIT – MST++

MST++ (multi-stage spectral-wise transformer) employs spectral-wise multi-head self-attention (S-MSA) in its basic unit: spectral-wise attention block (SAB). Each spectral feature map is treated as in S-MSA as a token to calculate the spectral self-attention. SABs form a U-shaped single-stage spectral-wise transformer (SST) to extract multi-resolution contextual information. MST++ is cascaded by several SSTs to enhance the reconstruction quality from coarse to fine.

In our study, the network was implemented according to the suggestions in [79]. The dimensions of the input RGB patch of the network were $128 \times 128 \times 3$, and of the output patch were $128 \times 128 \times 1$. It is noted that the original output bands for AWAN were 31, but in our case, it is only the NIR band. Thus, a convolutional layer was added after the output layer to produce 1 band instead of 31. To retain consistency with Pix2Pix, L1 loss was used. For fair comparison, it was decided to train for a similar amount of time as Pix2Pix, thus, the batch size and the number of training steps were set accordingly. The training details are shown in Table 2. The learning rate was set to 1×10^{-4} . The inference time for a 17 km^2 image was 92 s.

4) UNPAIRED ITIT (UDA) – CYCLEGAN

CycleGAN performs unpaired ITIT with adversarial training. Since the $G : x \rightarrow y$ mapping is under-constrained, an inverse mapping $F : y \rightarrow x$ is also employed and a Cycle-consistency loss is introduced to impose $F(G(x)) \approx x$ and

FIGURE 5. NIR spectral plots in paired ITIT (first stage). (a) Impervious, (b) Vegetation, (c) Ground.

$G(F(y)) \approx y$ (6).

$$L_{cyc}(G, F) = \mathbb{E}_x [\|F(G(x)) - x\|_1] + \mathbb{E}_y [\|G(F(y)) - y\|_1] \quad (6)$$

Both mappings are simultaneously trained. The objective function is a combination of the cycle-consistency loss and the adversarial losses. Two discriminators (D_x, D_y) are included in CycleGAN, one for each mapping. D_x aims at differentiating x from $F(y)$, and D_y aims at distinguishing y from $G(x)$. Except for the adversarial losses for the $G : x \rightarrow y$ and $F : y \rightarrow x$ mapping and the corresponding

discriminators (D_y, D_x), as suggested in [54], an identity loss (7) [82] is additionally utilized to retain color fidelity between the input and the output. Thus, the full objective is expressed in 8.

$$L_{identity}(G, F) = \mathbb{E}_y [\|G(y) - y\|_1] + \mathbb{E}_x [\|F(x) - x\|_1] \quad (7)$$

$$L(G, F, D_x, D_y) = L_{GAN}(G, D_y) + L_{GAN}(F, D_x) + \lambda_1 L_{cyc}(G, F) + \lambda_2 L_{identity}(G, F) \quad (8)$$

where $\lambda_1:10$ and $\lambda_2:5$

FIGURE 6. Samples of pseudo-color composites of the NIR predictions in the paired ITIT (first stage). Red color is assigned to the NIR band, green color to the RED band, and blue color to the GREEN band. (a1-a7) Natural RGB composite, (b1-b7) Ground-truth, (c1-c7) Pix2Pix, (d1-d7) AWAN, (e1-e7) MST++.

In our study, CycleGAN was implemented according to the suggestions in [54]. It is noted that three versions, which differed in the use of normalization layers and batch size, were explored. In the original paper, IN was used in the generator and BN in the discriminator. In the first and second versions, IN was employed in the generator and the discriminator with batch sizes 1 and 14 (maximum capacity of the available computer memory), respectively. In the third version, BN was

employed with a batch size of 14. All three versions were trained on the G1/G2 (GIN1, GIN14, GBN14) and the V1/V2 (VIN1, VIN14, VBN14) RGB pair of images.

The architecture of the three versions is shown in Fig. 2. Three convolutional layers and nine residual blocks formed the first version generator encoder, and two Upsampling and three convolutional layers formed the generator decoder. The PatchGAN discriminator consisted of five convolutional

TABLE 3. UDA - training details.

Training details	GIN1	GIN14	GBN14	VIN1	VIN14	VBN14
Epochs	200	80	80	200	80	80
Batch size	1	14	14	1	14	14
Patch size	256	256	256	256	256	256
Training steps	1312	1312	1312	1092	1092	1092
Trainable params G	716K	273K	273K	716K	273K	273K
Trainable params D	175K	43K	43K	175K	43K	43K
Training time	8	26	24	7	21	20
GPU memory usage (GB)	0.5	6	6	0.5	6	6

layers. In the second and third versions, the difference compared to the first version architecture was the use of three residual blocks instead of nine in the generator, and the removal of a convolutional layer (shown in yellow highlight) in the discriminator to alleviate the computational load. The learning rate for the first version was set constant to 2×10^{-4} for the first 100 epochs, and then linear decay to zero was implemented. For the second and third versions, the learning rate decay was implemented for the last ten epochs. Finally, the dimensions of the generator input and output patch were $256 \times 256 \times 3$ (RGB). It is noted that since CycleGAN aims at unpaired ITIT, realA and realB patches (Fig. 2) did not geographically match during training, since they were selected randomly.

The training details for the three versions are shown in Table 3. The inference time for a batch of 32 patches for the first version was 0.113 s, and for the second and third was 0.073 s. The selection of the final weights was based on the lowest cycle-consistency loss, along with observing image samples.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. PAIRED ITIT – FIRST STAGE

The results of the paired ITIT were evaluated quantitatively and qualitatively. For the quantitative evaluation, the root mean square error (RMSE) (9) and the structural similarity (SSIM) (10) [83] were calculated between the predicted NIR and the ground-truth with kernel size 7×7 . It is noted that RMSE is sensitive to spectral information, whereas SSIM is sensitive to geometry. In this paper, more importance is assigned to the accuracy of spectral representation.

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{n}} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{SSIM} = \frac{(2\mu_y\mu_{\hat{y}} + c_1)(2\sigma_{y\hat{y}} + c_2)}{(\mu_y^2 + \mu_{\hat{y}}^2 + c_1)(\sigma_y^2 + \sigma_{\hat{y}}^2 + c_2)} \quad (10)$$

where $c_1 = (k_1L)^3$, $c_2 = (k_2L)^3$, L : the dynamic range of the pixel values, $k_1=0.01$, and $k_2=0.03$.

FIGURE 7. Sample of G1 training image. (a) Natural RGB composite, (b) Pseudo-color composite containing NIR (Red color: NIR band, green color: RED band, blue color: GREEN band).

1) QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION – EVALUATION SCORES

RMSE and SSIM were estimated for the predicted images produced by Pix2Pix, AWAN, and MST++. It is noted that in contrast to the suggestion in [55], for Pix2Pix, BN was retained in the inference and was not changed to IN because it performed better in preliminary experiments. The scores were calculated for three separate categories: impervious (e.g., buildings, roads); vegetation (forest, crops); and ground. The three categories in the images were delineated by masks that were created in a graphics editor [84]. At first, vegetation was detected by the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) [85], and then the ground category was manually masked. The remaining area constituted the impervious category. The evaluation scores are presented in Table 4. The bold font indicates the best scores. The mean score values are depicted for each image. Total mean is the average of the mean values for all out-of-domain images.

As explained in section II-B, all models were trained on the G1 image alone and were evaluated on out-of-domain sets (G2, R1, R2, T1, T2, V1, V2). As already mentioned, the out-of-domain evaluation permits the performance estimation when the unavailable NIR image (e.g., airborne photo before the 2010s) corresponds to a spectrally similar area with available NIR.

By observing Table 4, it can be observed that in all three categories, MST++ showed the best overall performance in RMSE and SSIM, followed by AWAN and Pix2Pix. The vegetation category appeared to be the most difficult task (total mean RMSE: MST++: 0.128; AWAN: 0.143; Pix2Pix: 0.164). It is noted that in the impervious category, all models showed the worst scores in T1, T2 because the urban fabric spectral characteristics were highly different compared to G1 (different structures/materials). Similarly, regarding vegetation, the least satisfactory performance for all models was also shown in Tønsberg. However, V2 also presented high RMSE and low SSIM. Finally, in the ground category, T1 showed the worst scores.

2) QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION –BOXPLOTS

Except for quantitatively assessing the paired ITIT by the mean score values, boxplots were also created (Figs. 3, 4). In the boxplots, the first (Q1), second (Q2), and third (Q3) quartiles are depicted. The conclusions produced by observing Table 4 are consistent with the conclusions drawn by the

TABLE 4. NIR evaluation scores in paired ITIT – first stage.

		impervious			vegetation			ground		
		Pix2Pix	AWAN	MST++	Pix2Pix	AWAN	MST++	Pix2Pix	AWAN	MST++
			0.069	0.049	0.044	0.125	0.099	0.092	0.060	0.051
RMSE→	G2	0.069	0.049	0.044	0.125	0.099	0.092	0.060	0.051	0.045
	R1	0.094	0.079	0.069	0.144	0.076	0.102	0.096	0.078	0.072
	R2	0.129	0.128	0.106	0.141	0.126	0.097	0.096	0.107	0.082
	T1	0.180	0.160	0.168	0.187	0.162	0.139	0.190	0.195	0.201
	T2	0.185	0.170	0.170	0.220	0.222	0.187	0.115	0.136	0.099
	V1	0.089	0.081	0.070	0.131	0.135	0.122	No data		
	V2	0.114	0.101	0.100	0.196	0.182	0.160	No data		
	total mean	0.123	0.110	0.104	0.164	0.143	0.128	0.111	0.113	0.100
SSIM→	G2	0.883	0.953	0.961	0.774	0.861	0.889	0.878	0.948	0.959
	R1	0.843	0.913	0.927	0.599	0.858	0.860	0.741	0.902	0.931
	R2	0.847	0.900	0.927	0.702	0.828	0.871	0.834	0.921	0.950
	T1	0.641	0.731	0.736	0.665	0.746	0.802	0.744	0.870	0.870
	T2	0.614	0.726	0.727	0.656	0.672	0.775	0.757	0.856	0.885
	V1	0.868	0.917	0.932	0.605	0.740	0.765	No data		
	V2	0.821	0.877	0.882	0.537	0.639	0.683	No data		
	total mean	0.788	0.860	0.870	0.648	0.763	0.807	0.791	0.899	0.919

TABLE 5. NIR evaluation scores in paired ITIT after UDA.

	RMSE↓						SSIM↑					
	G2			V2			G2			V2		
	impervious	vegetation	ground	impervious	vegetation	ground	impervious	vegetation	ground	impervious	vegetation	ground
	Pix2Pix											
Before UDA	0.069	0.125	0.060	0.114	0.196	No data	0.883	0.774	0.878	0.821	0.537	No data
IN1	0.147	0.222	0.107	0.164	0.194	No data	0.472	0.336	0.361	0.513	0.357	No data
IN14	0.122	0.207	0.098	0.139	0.169	No data	0.598	0.442	0.502	0.662	0.460	No data
BN14	0.089	0.142	0.063	0.101	0.130	No data	0.744	0.607	0.715	0.793	0.586	No data
HM	0.070	0.152	0.063	0.114	0.156	No data	0.881	0.749	0.879	0.838	0.615	No data
	AWAN											
Before UDA	0.049	0.099	0.051	0.101	0.182	No data	0.953	0.861	0.948	0.877	0.639	No data
IN1	0.146	0.226	0.106	0.182	0.200	No data	0.475	0.334	0.373	0.502	0.366	No data
IN14	0.117	0.204	0.096	0.151	0.173	No data	0.617	0.462	0.529	0.664	0.491	No data
BN14	0.081	0.176	0.059	0.115	0.145	No data	0.785	0.632	0.770	0.814	0.628	No data
HM	0.048	0.123	0.052	0.134	0.179	No data	0.955	0.846	0.947	0.848	0.636	No data
	MST++											
Before UDA	0.044	0.092	0.045	0.100	0.160	No data	0.961	0.889	0.959	0.882	0.683	No data
IN1	0.144	0.209	0.101	0.167	0.188	No data	0.484	0.357	0.379	0.521	0.386	No data
IN14	0.115	0.186	0.094	0.137	0.157	No data	0.625	0.492	0.539	0.683	0.517	No data
BN14	0.078	0.142	0.060	0.098	0.123	No data	0.795	0.684	0.776	0.833	0.671	No data
HM	0.045	0.106	0.051	0.124	0.151	No data	0.961	0.880	0.955	0.874	0.709	No data

boxplots. It is observed that MST++ showed overall, the best performance followed by AWAN and Pix2Pix.

3) QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION –SPECTRAL PLOTS

To reinforce the visual perception of the results, spectral plots are depicted in Fig. 5. It is noted that since the NIR values correspond to only one band, the spectral curves are diminished to points. Thus, spectral plots were created as follows: At first, the mean values in the ranges: [0.2-0.21]; [0.3-0.31];

[0.4-0.41]; [0.5-0.51]; [0.6-0.61]; [0.7-0.71]; and [0.8-0.81] were calculated for the ground-truth NIR values in each of the three land cover categories. Then, the mean values for the same ranges were calculated for the predictions. As a final step, since predicted and ground-truth values were too close to be discernible in the plot, it was decided to subtract the ground-truth NIR values. Thus, in Fig. 5, y=0 corresponds to the ground-truth NIR values. The closest values to y=0 correspond to mean values closer to the ground-truth.

FIGURE 8. Boxplots of the evaluation scores in paired ITIT after UDA for the G2 region. (a) Impervious, (b) Vegetation, (c) Ground.

FIGURE 9. Boxplots of the evaluation scores in paired ITIT after UDA for the V2 region. (a) Impervious, (b) Vegetation.

It was observed that in the impervious category, MST++ showed the closest predictions to the ground-truth for most of the images, followed by AWAN and Pix2Pix. The same conclusion can be drawn for the vegetation category. Concerning the ground class, there is less agreement with Table 4, compared to the impervious and vegetation categories.

The fact that the spectral plots are not always in agreement with the scores in Table 4 illustrates how different metrics can provide different perspectives on image similarity, which can lead to variable conclusions, a known issue in the research community [86]. In this study, RMSE and SSIM employ a detailed spectral comparison through a 7×7 window, and thus are more trustworthy metrics than the spectral plots.

4) QUALITATIVE EVALUATION

The qualitative evaluation was conducted by visual interpretation, and it is complementary to the quantitative (Table 4). Samples of pseudo-color composites of the NIR predictions are displayed in Fig. 6. It is noted that it was decided to include pseudo-color composites in the paper instead of the grayscale NIR band to facilitate the visual interpretation. Red

color is assigned to the NIR band, green color to the RED band, and blue color to the GREEN band. Fig. 6 shows output samples for each of the seven images (G2, R1, R2, T1, T2, V1, V2) for the three trained models (Pix2Pix, AWAN, MST++). A sample of G1 (training image) is shown in Fig. 7.

Concerning the depiction of the impervious category in Fig. 6, the performance difference among the models can be visually perceived in: a) where Pix2Pix is outperformed in the spectral representation of buildings by MST++ and AWAN; b) R1, with MST++ and AWAN predictions showing better spectral similarity to the ground-truth compared to Pix2Pix; and c) V1, where MST++ outperforms the other two models. It is noted that predictions with $RMSE \approx 0.08$ do not visually differ from the ground-truth.

Regarding the depiction of the vegetation category in Fig. 6, the performance differences among the models are visually perceivable in several images: a) G2, where MST++ and AWAN show more satisfactory predicted values compared to Pix2Pix (e.g. top left); b) R1, with AWAN showing the best prediction, followed by MST++; c) R2, where MST++ and AWAN outperform Pix2Pix; d) T2, illustrating MST++ with higher NIR values, which are closer to the original; and e) V1, displaying MST++ as more spectrally similar to the ground-truth. It's noted that predictions with $RMSE \approx 1$ are visually very close to the ground-truth.

Finally, in the ground category, the performance difference among the models can be visually perceived in Fig. 6 in: a) R1 with Pix2Pix showing lower color resemblance compared to the other two models; b) R2 with MST++ depicting higher spectral similarity to the ground-truth; and c) T2 where MST++ (low left edge) predicts more accurately the original values.

B. PAIRED ITIT – AFTER UDA

As explained in section II-B, in this study, UDA (unpaired ITIT) was also implemented to improve the NIR prediction of G2 and V2 (produced by Pix2Pix, AWAN, and MST++)

FIGURE 10. NIR spectral plots in paired ITIT after UDA for the G2 region. (a) Impervious, (b) Vegetation, (c) Ground.

regarding the paired ITIT of the first stage. The UDA aimed at adapting G2 data to G1, and V2 data to V1, and thus increasing radiometric similarity based: a) on the logical assumption that the G1-trained models (Fig. 1/ Paired ITIT (1)) should perform better on G1 compared to G2, since G1 was the training set; and b) based on the fact that the G1-trained models performed better on V1 compared to V2 (Table 4).

In more detail, the three G2 and V2 domain-adapted RGB outputs produced by CycleGAN (IN1, IN14, BN14), acted as input to the G1-trained Pix2Pix, AWAN, and MST++ models (Fig. 1. / Paired ITIT (2)), and inference was implemented. The results of the inference (NIR predictions with domain-adapted RGB inputs) were compared with the initial predictions (before UDA) through RMSE and SSIM scores (kernel size: 7×7), as well as qualitatively. The effect of different normalization techniques (BN, IN) and batch sizes (1, 14) was evaluated. It is noted that besides the CycleGAN-based UDA, HM was also performed for comparison.

As already mentioned in section II-B, the Granada and Venice pairs were chosen to minimize seasonal variation, as they were gathered during the same month. G2 and V2 are deemed out-of-domain data in comparison to G1. G2 was gathered using a different sensor and at a different time, whereas V2 represents a different region.

1) QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION – EVALUATION SCORES

The RMSE and SSIM scores are presented in Table 5. It is observed that the NIR predictions of all three models (Pix2Pix, AWAN, MST++) on the outputs of the BN14 CycleGAN version, were significantly enhanced in terms of RMSE compared to the ones before UDA for the vegetation category in the V2 region. In more detail, the RMSE improved in a) Pix2Pix from 0.196 to 0.130; b) AWAN from 0.182 to 0.145; and c) MST++ from 0.160 to 0.123. The respective V1 vegetation RMSE values (Table 4) were 0.131, 0.135, and 0.122. Thus, in Pix2Pix and MST++, the maximum possible NIR prediction enhancement in terms of

FIGURE 11. NIR spectral plots in paired ITIT after UDA for the V2 region. (a) Impervious, (b) Vegetation.

RMSE was achieved. A smaller RMSE improvement also occurred on the outputs of the IN14 CycleGAN version and HM. Consequently, BN versions of CycleGAN appear to be the most promising for the enhancement of high RMSE scores. It is noted that a significant SSIM change was not observed.

It is also remarked that notable RMSE improvements were not observed in G2 and the impervious V2 category. We believe that the reason is the fact that the initial RMSE scores (before UDA) in G2 were significantly lower than the one of V2 vegetation due to lower radiometric difference in the respective RGB domains, i.e. the G2 RGB radiometry was similar to G1 RGB, whereas the V2 RGB vegetation radiometry was highly dissimilar to V1 RGB.

2) QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION – BOXPLOTS

Boxplots were also created for the quantitative assessment (Figs. 8, 9). The observation of the boxplots leads to the same conclusions as the observation of Table 5. In more detail,

FIGURE 12. Samples of pseudo-color composites of the NIR predictions in paired ITIT after UDA. (a1-a6) Before UDA, (b1-b6) IN1, (c1-c6) IN14, (d1-d6) BN14, (e1-e6) HM.

the BN14 version of CycleGAN greatly improved the RMSE in all NIR prediction models (Pix2Pix, AWAN, MST++) compared to the ones before UDA for the vegetation category in V2. The outputs of the IN14 version and HM showed a smaller improvement. Significant advancements are not seen in G2 and the impervious V2 category.

3) QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION – SPECTRAL PLOTS

To enhance the visual interpretation of the results, spectral plots are depicted in Figs. 10, 11. The approach used to create the curves is already explained in section III-A3.

The spectral plots referring to G2 (Fig. 10) are in agreement with Table 5, i.e., substantial improvements did not occur for any of the three land cover classes. As already mentioned, the reason for this could be the much lower initial RMSE scores (before UDA) compared to those of the V2 vegetation due to higher radiometric similarity in the respective RGB domains. Regarding the spectral plots referring to V2 (Fig. 11), for the vegetation category, the superiority of the BN14 CycleGAN version is once again highlighted for the three NIR prediction

models (Pix2Pix, AWAN, MST++), as it showed the closest predictions to the ground-truth.

It is noted that in the impervious category of V2, the spectral plots corresponding to the BN14 CycleGAN version of Pix2Pix and MST++ also show the closest predictions to the ground-truth. However, since this conclusion is not rigidly supported in Table 5, it is not considered trustworthy. As already mentioned in section III-A3, the RMSE score implements a more detailed spectral comparison, thus, in this paper it carries more weight.

4) QUALITATIVE EVALUATION

The qualitative evaluation was conducted by visual interpretation in addition to the quantitative (Table 5). Samples of pseudo-color composites of the NIR predictions are displayed in Fig. 12. This figure shows the outputs of the three NIR prediction models (Pix2Pix, AWAN, MST++) when feeding the domain-adapted RGB CycleGAN outputs (IN1, IN14, BN14) as well as the HM-adapted images. The ground-truth and the NIR predictions before UDA are also shown.

In Fig. 12, it can be visually perceived that the BN14 version of CycleGAN managed to produce the best enhancement in the spectral similarity of the vegetation V2 NIR prediction to the ground-truth in Pix2Pix, AWAN, and MST++. The IN14 version of CycleGAN and HM produced smaller enhancements. Significant improvement is not seen in G2 and the impervious V2 category.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, a conditional GAN (Pix2Pix) and two attention networks (AWAN, MST++) were initially assessed on predicting NIR on out-of-domain RGB bi-temporal data. The properties of the out-of-domain RGB data were those typically required in RS NIR prediction tasks: different regions/sensors/dates than the training set. The three NIR prediction models were trained in a single Granada image (G1) and evaluated on seven out-of-domain heterogeneous images referring to Granada, Rhodes, Tønsberg, and Venice (G2, R1, R2, T1, T2, V1, V2). It is remarked that former research regarding NIR prediction on out-of-domain data is extremely scarce. However, such research is significant for the NIR enrichment of a) airborne RGB images collected before the 2010s, when NIR imagery was limited; and b) a large number of public annotated RGB datasets often used as benchmarks.

It is also remarked that attention models have not been tested before in the RGB-to-NIR translation.

In a subsequent step, the study's attention was directed toward the increase of the radiometric similarity between the source and target RGB data by employing CycleGAN-based unsupervised domain adaptation (UDA) on unpaired data. The ultimate objective of UDA was the improvement of the initial NIR prediction. The unpaired process followed a more general scenario where the source and target RGB patches used in the CycleGAN training did not geographically correspond. To implement the UDA, three CycleGAN versions (IN1, IN14, BN14) were explored, where the effect of different normalization techniques (batch normalization (BN), instance normalization (IN)) and batch sizes (1, 14) was evaluated. To implement the UDA, bi-temporal pairs collected on the same month to avoid seasonal changes were selected. Thus, the aim was to adapt G2 (target) to G1 (source) and V2 (target) to V1 (source) based: a) on the logical assumption that the G1-trained models should perform better on G1 compared to G2, since G1 was the training set; and b) based on the fact that the G1-trained models predicted NIR more accurately on V1 compared to V2. It is highlighted that through this study, UDA is employed for the first time in the enhancement of cross-domain band generation.

In all NIR prediction experiments, the assessment was conducted quantitatively and qualitatively on three main land cover categories (impervious surfaces/urban fabric, vegetation, ground), thus, contrary to prior work, the impervious and ground classes were not overlooked.

It was shown that MST++ (vision transformer) produced the most satisfactory out-of-domain NIR predictions in all

three land cover classes and that UDA through the BN14 CycleGAN version managed to significantly enhance the NIR prediction when there was a substantial RGB radiometric difference (radiometric domain gap).

For future work, the prediction of shortwave-infrared (SWIR) information will be explored. In addition, the feasibility of UDA between different geographic areas with similar spectral characteristics and the spectral enrichment of annotated public datasets will be investigated.

REFERENCES

- [1] X. Li, Z. Du, Y. Huang, and Z. Tan, "A deep translation (GAN) based change detection network for optical and SAR remote sensing images," *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens.*, vol. 179, pp. 14–34, Sep. 2021.
- [2] Z. Guo, H. Guo, X. Liu, W. Zhou, Y. Wang, and Y. Fan, "Sar2color: Learning imaging characteristics of SAR images for SAR-to-optical transformation," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 14, no. 15, p. 3740, Aug. 2022.
- [3] J. Wei, H. Zou, L. Sun, X. Cao, S. He, S. Liu, and Y. Zhang, "CFRWD-GAN for SAR-to-optical image translation," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 15, no. 10, p. 2547, May 2023.
- [4] Y. Pan, I. A. Khan, and H. Meng, "SAR-to-optical image translation using multi-stream deep ResCNN of information reconstruction," *Expert Syst. Appl.*, vol. 224, Aug. 2023, Art. no. 120040.
- [5] Q. Luo, H. Li, Z. Chen, and J. Li, "ADD-UNet: An adjacent dual-decoder UNet for SAR-to-optical translation," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 15, no. 12, p. 3125, Jun. 2023.
- [6] C. Zhang, Y. Feng, L. Hu, D. Tapete, L. Pan, Z. Liang, F. Cigna, and P. Yue, "A domain adaptation neural network for change detection with heterogeneous optical and SAR remote sensing images," *Int. J. Appl. Earth Observ. Geoinf.*, vol. 109, May 2022, Art. no. 102769.
- [7] A. Manocha and Y. Afaq, "Optical and SAR images-based image translation for change detection using generative adversarial network (GAN)," *Multimedia Tools Appl.*, vol. 82, no. 17, pp. 26289–26315, Jul. 2023.
- [8] Y. Qing, J. Zhu, H. Feng, W. Liu, and B. Wen, "Two-way generation of high-resolution EO and SAR images via dual distortion-adaptive GANs," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 15, no. 7, p. 1878, Mar. 2023.
- [9] H. Wang, Z. Zhang, Z. Hu, and Q. Dong, "SAR-to-optical image translation with hierarchical latent features," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 60, 2022, Art. no. 9864654. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9864654>
- [10] Y. Liu, W. Wang, F. Fang, L. Zhou, C. Sun, Y. Zheng, and Z. Chen, "CscGAN: Conditional scale-consistent generation network for multi-level remote sensing image to map translation," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 13, no. 10, p. 1936, May 2021.
- [11] X. Chen, S. Chen, T. Xu, B. Yin, J. Peng, X. Mei, and H. Li, "SMAP-GAN: Generative adversarial network-based semisupervised styled map tile generation method," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 59, no. 5, pp. 4388–4406, May 2021.
- [12] J. Song, J. Li, H. Chen, and J. Wu, "RSMT: A remote sensing image-to-map translation model via adversarial deep transfer learning," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 14, no. 4, p. 919, Feb. 2022.
- [13] Y. Fu, Z. Fang, L. Chen, T. Song, and D. Lin, "Level-aware consistent multilevel map translation from satellite imagery," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 61, 2023, Art. no. 9950295. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9950295>
- [14] J. Song, H. Chen, C. Du, and J. Li, "Semi-MapGAN: Translation of remote sensing image into map via semisupervised adversarial learning," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 61, 2023, Art. no. 10091136. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10091136>
- [15] P. Ghamisi and N. Yokoya, "IMG2DSM: Height simulation from single imagery using conditional generative adversarial net," *IEEE Geosci. Remote Sens. Lett.*, vol. 15, no. 5, pp. 794–798, May 2018.
- [16] E. Panagiotou, G. Chochlakakis, L. Grammatikopoulos, and E. Charou, "Generating elevation surface from a single RGB remotely sensed image using deep learning," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 12, no. 12, p. 2002, Jun. 2020.
- [17] H. A. Amirkolaee and H. Arefi, "Height estimation from single aerial images using a deep convolutional encoder–decoder network," *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens.*, vol. 149, pp. 50–66, Mar. 2019.

- [18] S. Karatsiolis, A. Kamilaris, and I. Cole, "IMG2nDSM: Height estimation from single airborne RGB images with deep learning," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 13, no. 12, p. 2417, Jun. 2021.
- [19] K. Kim, J.-H. Kim, Y.-J. Moon, E. Park, G. Shin, T. Kim, Y. Kim, and S. Hong, "Nighttime reflectance generation in the visible band of satellites," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 11, no. 18, p. 2087, Sep. 2019.
- [20] J.-H. Kim, S. Ryu, J. Jeong, D. So, H.-J. Ban, and S. Hong, "Impact of satellite sounding data on virtual visible imagery generation using conditional generative adversarial network," *IEEE J. Sel. Topics Appl. Earth Observ. Remote Sens.*, vol. 13, pp. 4532–4541, 2020.
- [21] K.-H. Han, J.-C. Jang, S. Ryu, E.-H. Sohn, and S. Hong, "Hypothetical visible bands of advanced meteorological imager onboard the geostationary Korea multi-purpose Satellite-2A using data-to-data translation," *IEEE J. Sel. Topics Appl. Earth Observ. Remote Sens.*, vol. 15, pp. 8378–8388, 2022.
- [22] J. Xiao, D. Tortei, E. Roura, and G. Loianno, "Long-range UAV thermal geo-localization with satellite imagery," in *Proc. IEEE/RSJ Int. Conf. Intell. Robots Syst. (IROS)*, Oct. 2023, pp. 5820–5827.
- [23] J.-E. Park, G. Kim, and S. Hong, "Green band generation for advanced baseline imager sensor using Pix2Pix with advanced baseline imager and advanced Himawari imager observations," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 59, no. 8, pp. 6415–6423, Aug. 2021.
- [24] H.-S. Ryu, J.-E. Park, J. Jeong, and S. Hong, "Generation of hypothetical radiances for missing green and red bands in geostationary environment monitoring spectrometer," *IEEE J. Sel. Topics Appl. Earth Observ. Remote Sens.*, vol. 16, pp. 9025–9037, 2023.
- [25] M. Wu, X. Jin, Q. Jiang, S.-J. Lee, W. Liang, G. Lin, and S. Yao, "Remote sensing image colorization using symmetrical multi-scale DCGAN in YUV color space," *Vis. Comput.*, vol. 37, no. 7, pp. 1707–1729, Jul. 2021.
- [26] M. Wu, X. Jin, Q. Jiang, S.-J. Lee, L. Guo, Y. Di, S. Huang, and J. Huang, "Remote sensing image colorization based on multiscale SENet GAN," in *Proc. 12th Int. Congr. Image Signal Process., Biomed. Eng. Informat. (CISP-BMEI)*, Oct. 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [27] S. Galliani, C. Lanaras, D. Marmaris, E. Baltsavias, and K. Schindler, "Learned spectral super-resolution," 2017, *arXiv:1703.09470*.
- [28] S. Paul and D. N. Kumar, "Transformation of multispectral data to quasi-hyperspectral data using convolutional neural network regression," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 59, no. 4, pp. 3352–3368, Apr. 2021.
- [29] L. Liu, S. Lei, Z. Shi, N. Zhang, and X. Zhu, "Hyperspectral remote sensing image generation from RGB images based on joint discrimination," *IEEE J. Sel. Topics Appl. Earth Observ. Remote Sens.*, vol. 14, pp. 7624–7636, 2021.
- [30] L. Liu, Z. Shi, Y. Zao, and H. Chen, "Hyperspectral image generation from RGB images with semantic and spatial distribution consistency," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Geosci. Remote Sens. Symp.*, Jul. 2022, pp. 1804–1807.
- [31] S. Liu, H. Li, G. Zhang, B. Hu, and J. Chen, "Using hyperspectral reconstruction for multispectral images change detection," in *Proc. 7th Int. Conf. Image, Vis. Comput. (ICIVC)*, Jul. 2022, pp. 183–188.
- [32] L. Deng, J. Sun, Y. Chen, H. Lu, F. Duan, L. Zhu, and T. Fan, "M2H-net: A reconstruction method for hyperspectral remotely sensed imagery," *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens.*, vol. 173, pp. 323–348, Mar. 2021.
- [33] T. Li and Y. Gu, "Progressive spatial-spectral joint network for hyperspectral image reconstruction," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 60, 2022, Art. no. 9439796. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9439796>
- [34] X. Zheng, W. Chen, and X. Lu, "Spectral super-resolution of multispectral images using spatial-spectral residual attention network," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 60, 2022, Art. no. 9519844. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9519844>
- [35] Z. Liu, H. Zhu, and Z. Chen, "Adversarial spectral super-resolution for multispectral imagery using spatial spectral feature attention module," *IEEE J. Sel. Topics Appl. Earth Observ. Remote Sens.*, vol. 16, pp. 1550–1562, 2023.
- [36] G. Zhao, Y. He, Z. Wang, and H. Wu, "Hybrid transformer architecture for spectral super-resolution reconstruction of multispectral images," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Geosci. Remote Sens. Symp.*, Jul. 2024, pp. 9468–9471.
- [37] N. Wang, S. Mei, Y. Zhang, M. Ma, and X. Zhang, "Hyperspectral image reconstruction from RGB input through highlighting intrinsic properties," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 62, 2024, Art. no. 10620339. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10620339>
- [38] H. Zhou, Z. Liu, Z. Huang, X. Wang, W. Su, and Y. Zhang, "ICTH: Local-to-global spectral reconstruction network for heterosource hyperspectral images," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 16, no. 18, p. 3377, Sep. 2024.
- [39] M. Aslahishahri, K. G. Stanley, H. Duddu, S. Shirliffle, S. Vail, K. Bett, C. Pozniak, and I. Stavness, "From RGB to NIR: Predicting of near infrared reflectance from visible spectrum aerial images of crops," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Int. Conf. Comput. Vis. Workshops (ICCVW)*, Oct. 2021, pp. 1312–1322.
- [40] S. Illarionova, D. Shadrin, A. Trekin, V. Ignatiev, and I. Oseledets, "Generation of the NIR spectral band for satellite images with convolutional neural networks," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 16, p. 5646, Aug. 2021.
- [41] D. C. de Lima, D. Saqui, S. A. T. Mpinda, and J. H. Saito, "Pix2Pix network to estimate agricultural near infrared images from RGB data," *Can. J. Remote Sens.*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 299–315, Mar. 2022.
- [42] A. Picon, A. Bereciartua-Perez, I. Eguskiza, J. Romero-Rodriguez, C. J. Jimenez-Ruiz, T. Eggers, C. Klukas, and R. Navarra-Mestre, "Deep convolutional neural network for damaged vegetation segmentation from RGB images based on virtual NIR-channel estimation," *Artif. Intell. Agricult.*, vol. 6, pp. 199–210, Jan. 2022.
- [43] X. Yuan, J. Tian, and P. Reinartz, "Learning-based near-infrared band simulation with applications on large-scale landcover classification," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 9, p. 4179, Apr. 2023.
- [44] Y. Cai, Y. Yang, Q. Zheng, Z. Shen, Y. Shang, J. Yin, and Z. Shi, "BiFDANet: Unsupervised bidirectional domain adaptation for semantic segmentation of remote sensing images," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 190, Jan. 2022.
- [45] Y. Zhao, P. Guo, Z. Sun, X. Chen, and H. Gao, "ResiDualGAN: Resize-residual DualGAN for cross-domain remote sensing images semantic segmentation," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 15, no. 5, p. 1428, Mar. 2023.
- [46] S. Luo, L. Ma, X. Yang, D. Luo, and Q. Du, "Self-training-based unsupervised domain adaptation for object detection in remote sensing imagery," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 62, 2024, Art. no. 10677431. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10677431>
- [47] J. Zeng, Y. Gu, C. Qin, X. Jia, S. Deng, J. Xu, and H. Tian, "Unsupervised domain adaptation for remote sensing semantic segmentation with the 2D discrete wavelet transform," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 23552, Oct. 2024.
- [48] K. Sasaki, T. Sekine, and W. Emery, "Enhancing the detection of coastal marine debris in very high-resolution satellite imagery via unsupervised domain adaptation," *IEEE J. Sel. Topics Appl. Earth Observ. Remote Sens.*, vol. 17, pp. 6014–6028, 2024.
- [49] B. Zhang, T. Chen, and B. Wang, "Curriculum-style local-to-global adaptation for cross-domain remote sensing image segmentation," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 60, 2022, Art. no. 9576523. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9576523>
- [50] L. Wang, P. Xiao, X. Zhang, and X. Chen, "A fine-grained unsupervised domain adaptation framework for semantic segmentation of remote sensing images," *IEEE J. Sel. Topics Appl. Earth Observ. Remote Sens.*, vol. 16, pp. 4109–4121, 2023.
- [51] L. Wu, M. Lu, and L. Fang, "Deep covariance alignment for domain adaptive remote sensing image segmentation," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 60, 2022, Art. no. 9745130. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9745130>
- [52] S. F. Ismael, K. Kayabol, and E. Aptoula, "Unsupervised domain adaptation for the semantic segmentation of remote sensing images via one-shot image-to-image translation," *IEEE Geosci. Remote Sens. Lett.*, vol. 20, pp. 1–5, 2023.
- [53] R. Chen, W. Huang, B. Huang, F. Sun, and B. Fang, "Reusing discriminators for encoding: Towards unsupervised image-to-image translation," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. (CVPR)*, Jun. 2020, pp. 8165–8174.
- [54] J.-Y. Zhu, T. Park, P. Isola, and A. A. Efros, "Unpaired image-to-image translation using cycle-consistent adversarial networks," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Comput. Vis. (ICCV)*, Oct. 2017, pp. 2242–2251.
- [55] P. Isola, J.-Y. Zhu, T. Zhou, and A. A. Efros, "Image-to-image translation with conditional adversarial networks," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. (CVPR)*, Jul. 2017, pp. 5967–5976.
- [56] O. Ronneberger, P. Fischer, and T. Brox, "U-Net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation," in *Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention—MICCAI 2015*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2015, pp. 234–241.

- [57] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun, "Deep residual learning for image recognition," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. (CVPR)*, Jun. 2016, pp. 770–778.
- [58] V. Tiwari, V. Kumar, K. Pandey, R. Ranade, and S. Agrawal, "Simulation of the hyperspectral data using multispectral data," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Geosci. Remote Sens. Symp. (IGARSS)*, Jul. 2016, pp. 6157–6160.
- [59] N. T. Hoang and K. Koike, "Transformation of Landsat imagery into pseudo-hyperspectral imagery by a multiple regression-based model with application to metal deposit-related minerals mapping," *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens.*, vol. 133, pp. 157–173, Nov. 2017.
- [60] X. Han, J. Yu, J. Luo, and W. Sun, "Reconstruction from multispectral to hyperspectral image using spectral library-based dictionary learning," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 57, no. 3, pp. 1325–1335, Mar. 2019.
- [61] K. Fotiadou, G. Tsagkatakis, and P. Tsakalides, "Spectral super resolution of hyperspectral images via coupled dictionary learning," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 57, no. 5, pp. 2777–2797, May 2019.
- [62] S. Jégou, M. Drozdal, D. Vazquez, A. Romero, and Y. Bengio, "The one hundred layers tiramisu: Fully convolutional DenseNets for semantic segmentation," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. Workshops (CVPRW)*, Jul. 2017, pp. 1175–1183.
- [63] K. Arai, K. Gondoh, O. Shigetomi, and Yuko, "Method for NIR reflectance estimation with visible camera data based on regression for NDVI estimation and its application for insect damage detection of Rice paddy fields," *Int. J. Adv. Res. Artif. Intell.*, vol. 5, no. 11, pp. 17–22, Jan. 2016.
- [64] K. Arai, M. Sakashita, O. Shigetomi, and Y. Miura, "Estimation of protein content in Rice crop and nitrogen content in Rice leaves through regression analysis with NDVI derived from camera mounted radio-control helicopter," *Int. J. Adv. Res. Artif. Intell.*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 12–19, 2014.
- [65] P. Navarro, F. Pérez, J. Weiss, and M. Egea-Cortines, "Machine learning and computer vision system for phenotype data acquisition and analysis in plants," *Sensors*, vol. 16, no. 5, p. 641, May 2016.
- [66] W. Li, R. Dong, H. Fu, and L. Yu, "Large-scale oil palm tree detection from high-resolution satellite images using two-stage convolutional neural networks," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 11, Dec. 2018.
- [67] R. Szeliski, *Computer Vision: Algorithms and Applications*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2022.
- [68] D. C. de Lima, D. Saqui, S. Ataky, L. A. D. C. Jorge, E. J. Ferreira, and J. H. Saito, "Estimating agriculture NIR images from aerial RGB data," in *Computational Science—ICCS 2019*, vol. 11536. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2019, pp. 562–574.
- [69] MAXAR. *Satellite Imagery for Natural Disasters*. Accessed: Jul. 17, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.maxar.com/open-data>
- [70] R. Caye Daudt, B. Le Saux, A. Boulch, and Y. Gousseau, "Multitask learning for large-scale semantic change detection," *Comput. Vis. Image Understand.*, vol. 187, Oct. 2019, Art. no. 102783.
- [71] H. Chen and Z. Shi, "A spatial-temporal attention-based method and a new dataset for remote sensing image change detection," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 12, no. 10, p. 1662, May 2020.
- [72] J. Fan, T. Chen, and S. Lu, "Unsupervised feature learning for land-use scene recognition," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 55, no. 4, pp. 2250–2261, Apr. 2017.
- [73] R. Jain and R. U. Sharma, "Airborne hyperspectral data for mineral mapping in Southeastern Rajasthan, India," *Int. J. Appl. Earth Observ. Geoinformation*, vol. 81, pp. 137–145, Sep. 2019.
- [74] M. Kremezi, V. Kristollari, V. Karathanassi, K. Topouzelis, P. Kolokoussis, N. Taggio, A. Aiello, G. Ceriola, E. Barbone, and P. Corradi, "Pansharpening PRISMA data for marine plastic litter detection using plastic indexes," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 61955–61971, 2021.
- [75] M. Kremezi, V. Kristollari, V. Karathanassi, K. Topouzelis, P. Kolokoussis, N. Taggio, A. Aiello, G. Ceriola, E. Barbone, and P. Corradi, "Increasing the Sentinel-2 potential for marine plastic litter monitoring through image fusion techniques," *Mar. Pollut. Bull.*, vol. 182, Sep. 2022, Art. no. 113974.
- [76] X. Huang, D. Xu, Z. Li, and C. Wang, "Translating multispectral imagery to nighttime imagery via conditional generative adversarial networks," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Geosci. Remote Sens. Symp.*, Sep. 2020, pp. 6758–6761.
- [77] V. Kristollari and V. Karathanassi, "Change detection in VHR imagery with severe co-registration errors using deep learning: A comparative study," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 33723–33741, 2022.
- [78] J. Li, C. Wu, R. Song, Y. Li, and F. Liu, "Adaptive weighted attention network with camera spectral sensitivity prior for spectral reconstruction from RGB images," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. Workshops (CVPRW)*, Jun. 2020, pp. 1894–1903.
- [79] Y. Cai, J. Lin, Z. Lin, H. Wang, Y. Zhang, H. Pfister, R. Timofte, and L. V. Gool, "MST++: Multi-stage spectral-wise transformer for efficient spectral reconstruction," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. Workshops (CVPRW)*, Jun. 2022, pp. 744–754.
- [80] A. Paszke, "PyTorch: An imperative style, high-performance deep learning library," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, vol. 32, 2019, pp. 8026–8037.
- [81] I. Goodfellow, J. Pouget-Abadie, M. Mirza, B. Xu, D. Warde-Farley, S. Ozair, A. Courville, and Y. Bengio, "Generative adversarial networks," *Commun. ACM*, vol. 63, no. 11, pp. 139–144, Oct. 2020.
- [82] Y. Taigman, A. Polyak, and L. Wolf, "Unsupervised cross-domain image generation," 2016, *arXiv1611.02200*.
- [83] Z. Wang, A. C. Bovik, H. R. Sheikh, and E. P. Simoncelli, "Image quality assessment: From error visibility to structural similarity," *IEEE Trans. Image Process.*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 600–612, Apr. 2004.
- [84] *Adobe Photoshop*, Adobe Inc., San Jose, CA, USA.
- [85] J. Rouse, R. H. Haas, J. Schell, and D. W. Deering, "Monitoring vegetation systems in the great plains with ERTS," in *Proc. 3rd Earth Resour. Technol. Satellite-1 Symp.*, vol. 1, Jan. 1974, pp. 309–317.
- [86] H. B. Mitchell, "Image similarity measures," in *Image Fusion: Theories, Techniques and Applications*. Berlin, Germany: Springer, 2010, pp. 167–185.

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